

STUDY OF PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT AND EMOTIONAL SKILLS AMONG PRESCHOOLERS

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Paper Received On: 21 June 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 25 July 2025

Published On: 01 August 2025

Abstract

The current study examines the relationship between parental involvement and emotional skill acquisition among preschool children. Emotional skills like self-awareness, empathy, and emotional regulation are essential in early childhood, whereas parental involvement is considered an underlying influence for these skills. The study used a descriptive research design, applied self-constructed tools to determine parental engagement and preschoolers' emotional skills. Data were gathered from 100 parents of preschoolers studying in government as well as private schools. The statistical analysis was carried out using Pearson's correlation coefficient and t-tests. The results revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.669$, $p < 0.01$) between parental engagement and the emotional skill development of preschoolers. Moreover, the preschoolers enrolled in private schools have a higher mean score (4.12) than those in government schools (2.58), indicating a greater level of emotional development among children from private institutions. Also, no significant differences were seen between preschoolers' gender in emotional skills development.

Key words: Parental Engagement, Emotional Skills, Preschoolers

Introduction

Early childhood is a key period in the attainment of emotional competencies, and it provides the groundwork for a child's future social adjustment, academic achievement, and health (Denham, 2006). In these early years, children learn critical emotional skills like self-awareness, empathy, regulation of emotions, and social interaction skills. These are not fixed attributes that are merely inherited from parents, but are developed through in-depth social interactions with family, peers, and the larger community (Vygotsky, 1978). Among such social forces, parental engagement is especially crucial. Parental engagement with their children not only supplies the bare essentials, but rather, they provide emotional stability, persistent support, and a sense of safe haven from where children can venture out into the world (Morrison, 2014). The nature and extent of such engagement strongly determine how a child will recognize and regulate emotions, develop normal interpersonal relationships, and develop resilience (Thompson, 2014).

Emotional abilities are a basis of good development. They help children identify their own feelings, feel with the emotions of others, and effectively negotiate social interactions (Denham, 2006). They are associated with numerous long-term benefits when learned early, including improved school performance, improved mental health, and good relationships with peers. Research suggests that emotionally competent children find it easier to deal with stress, show fewer behavioral issues, and adapt better to school environments (Webster-Stratton & Reid, 2004). Emotional competence also results in increased empathy and thoughtfulness and a more social, tolerant, and charitable society.

Families, or parents at least, are significant partners on this development journey. Parental involvement encompasses a wide range of behaviors, such as participation in school events, collaboration in home learning, and open and supportive communication with children. These active participations provide children with a sense of safety and emotional stability, which is fundamental for their emotional development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Involved parents' children tend to show higher emotional competence, such as better emotion regulation, empathy, and social relationships. These children are also more likely to form secure attachments, which give them emotional support for early development.

Very emotionally intelligent children are likely to be better at handling interpersonal relationships in a sensitive and thoughtful way (Goleman, 1995). In line with this, research by Arslan et al. (2011) found positive correlations between social confidence, family participation, school readiness, and control of emotions.

Fundamentally, emotional development in early childhood is not a solitary endeavor but a collective responsibility, where families, particularly parents, take center stage. The objective of this study is to examine how the involvement of parents affects the development of emotional skills of preschoolers, with the belief that effective family participation can produce emotionally sound and socially competent generations.

Objectives of the study

The following objectives were formulated for the proposed study:

- 1) To study parental engagement and emotional skills among preschoolers.
- 2) To assess the emotional skills of preschoolers across developmental domains.
- 3) To compare the emotional skills of preschoolers based on gender.
- 4) To explore the relationship between parental engagement and emotional skills among preschoolers.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the proposed study:

- 1) There is no significant difference in the emotional skills of preschoolers based on school type (government vs private)
- 2) There is no significant difference in the emotional skills of preschoolers based on gender.
- 3) There is no relationship between parental engagement and emotional skills among preschoolers.

Tools used

The following tools were used for data collection:

- 1) Parental engagement scale (self-constructed).
- 2) Emotional skill checklist (self-constructed).

Statistical Treatment Analyses

The data were analysed by using the following statistical techniques:

- 1) Descriptive statistics including mean, standard deviation, and standard error.
- 2) Inferential statistics including t-test and Pearson correlation analysis.

Methodology

This paper used a descriptive research design to investigate the correlation between parental involvement and emotional skills of preschool children. The sample of 100 parents of preschool children was drawn by using the stratified random sampling method from

government and private schools. The tools were administered to the sample, and data were obtained, and statistical analysis were applied.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the emotional skills of preschoolers based on school type (Government vs Private).

Table 1.1

Group Statistics: Emotional Skills Based on School Type

Group Statistics		School type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Emotional Skills based on type of School		Government	50	2.58	.725	.103
		Private	50	4.12	.480	.068

Table 1.1 presents the mean scores of preschoolers from government and private schools with respect to their emotional development skills. The preschoolers enrolled in private schools have a higher mean score (4.12) than those in government schools (2.58), indicating a greater level of emotional development among children from private institutions. To further examine whether this difference is statistically significant, an Independent Samples t-test was conducted (see Table 1.2).

Table 1.2

Independent Samples t-Test: Emotional Skills and School Type

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
							Lower	Upper
13.698	.000	-12.559	98	.000	-1.544	.123	-1.788	-1.300
		-12.559	85.012	.000	-1.544	.123	-1.789	-1.300

The t-test results (t = -12.559, df = 85.012, p = .000) demonstrate that the mean difference of -1.544 is statistically significant, as the p-value is below the 0.05 threshold (see Table 1.2). The Independent Samples t-test revealed a statistically significant difference in emotional skills between government and private school preschoolers. The p-value (0.000) is significant at 0.05 level of significance which indicate that there is significant difference. This indicates that preschoolers from private schools exhibit significantly higher emotional skills

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than their counterparts in government schools. Hence, the null hypothesis stating “There is no significant difference in the emotional skills of preschoolers based on school type (Government vs Private)” is rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in emotional skills of preschoolers based on gender.

Table 1.3

Group Statistics: Emotional Skills based on Gender

		Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
		Girl/Boy				
Emotional Skills based on Gender	Girls		54	3.44	1.003	.137
	Boys		46	3.26	.976	.144

Table 1.4

Independent Samples t-Test: Emotional Skills based on Gender

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
							Lower	Upper	
.010	.920	.923	98	.358	.184	.199	-.211	.578	
		.925	96.251	.357	.184	.198	-.210	.577	

Table 1.3 presents the mean scores of preschoolers, i.e., boys and girls, with respect to their emotional skills. Girls have a slightly higher mean emotional skills score (3.44) compared to boys (3.26). To further examine whether this difference is statistically significant, an Independent Samples t-test was conducted (see Table 1.4).

The result of this test shows a p-value of 0.920, which is much greater than the common significance level of 0.05. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the variances of the two groups. Therefore, we can proceed with the assumption that equal variances exist between the groups, and the results from the "Equal variances assumed" row of the t-test are appropriate to interpret.

Following this, the independent samples t-test is used to compare the mean emotional development scores between boys and girls. The test statistic is $t(98) = 0.923$, with a corresponding p-value of 0.358. This p-value is substantially higher than 0.05, the threshold typically used to determine statistical significance.

Since the p-value exceeds 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. In other words, there is no statistically significant difference in the emotional development skills of boys and girls in this sample. The difference in mean scores (Girls = 3.44, Boys = 3.26) is relatively small and likely due to random variation rather than a true difference influenced by gender.

Although girls have a slightly higher mean emotional development score than boys, this difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, the analysis supports the null hypothesis that "There is no significant difference in emotional development skills based on gender."

Hypothesis 3: There is no relationship between parental engagement and emotional skills among preschoolers.

Table 1.5

Correlations: Parental Engagement and Emotional Skills among Preschoolers

		Parental Engagement	Emotional Skills
Parental Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1	.669**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Emotional Skills	Pearson Correlation	.669**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis show a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.669$ between parental engagement and emotional skills among preschoolers. This value falls within the range considered to represent a strong positive correlation (Table 1.6). This means that as parental engagement increases, the emotional skills of preschoolers also increase. In other words, higher levels of involvement by parents, such as helping with learning, showing emotional support, and consistent communication, are linked with better emotional development in children.

The p-value is 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01. This indicates that the observed correlation is statistically significant at the 1% level (2-tailed test). Therefore, based on the data, the researcher concludes that there is a meaningful relationship between parental engagement and emotional skills in the preschool population studied.

This indicates that parental engagement in preschoolers has a significant effect on the emotional skills of the children. The hypothesis that states "there is no relationship between parental engagement and emotional skills among preschoolers" is therefore rejected.

Table 1.6*Common Interpretation of Pearson's r (According to Cohen, 1988)*

Correlation Coefficient (r)	Strength of Relationship
0.10 to 0.29	Small / Weak
0.30 to 0.49	Medium / Moderate
0.50 to 1.00	Large / Strong

Discussion

The results show that preschool children attending private institutions are far better emotionally developed compared to children in government schools. This result indicates that the nature of the school has a significant effect on the development of emotional competencies in early childhood. This could be because private schools tend to provide more organized emotional and social training activities, improved teacher-student ratios, or increased parent-teacher interactions, all of which can positively enhance emotional skill building (Denham et al., 2012; Bierman et al., 2008). Results also show that gender has minimal roles in the learning of emotional skills during the preschool age. This is consistent with existing research, which maintains that although boys and girls may exhibit slight differences in feelings or behaviors at preschool age, these are not necessarily profound and widespread across contexts (Denham & Burton, 2003; Else-Quest et al., 2006). Another finding reveals that Children gain emotionally from having their parents involved in their daily lives, exhibit empathy and affection, and are assisted in their learning and emotional development in the home environment. The results are congruent with existing research that underscores the pivotal role that parents have in children's social and emotional development in early life (Fan & Chen, 2001; Sheridan et al., 2010).

Conclusion

The present study was undertaken to explore the relationship between parental engagement and the emotional skills of preschoolers. The findings indicate that parental involvement plays a pivotal role in shaping the emotional competencies of young children. Active and positive engagement by parents, through supportive communication, shared learning activities, and emotional responsiveness, contributes significantly to the development of self-awareness, emotional regulation, empathy, and social skills in preschool-aged children.

The study reinforces the importance of creating a nurturing home environment where children feel secure, valued, and emotionally supported. It also highlights how parents' involvement in early learning settings can bridge the gap between home and school, fostering

continuity in emotional skills development. As preschool years form the foundation for future emotional and academic success, this study emphasizes the need for educators, policymakers, and families to prioritize parental involvement as a core strategy for early childhood development.

Further, gender does not appear to play a significant role in influencing the emotional skills of preschool children, indicating that emotional development at this stage is shaped more by environmental and relational factors than by gender differences.

Moreover, the results of the research show that preschool children in private schools exhibit relatively better emotional skills compared to their government school counterparts. This would suggest that differences in school settings, resources, and parental engagement could account for differences in emotional skill among preschool children.

To sum up, this study adds weight to the body of literature that asserts that active parenting is not just desirable but a necessary ingredient for integral child development. The future work must be directed towards empowering parents with information, abilities, and infrastructural facilities so that they can be active agents in emotional development in their children at home and in school.

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